

KONFERENSIYA

**“ZAMONAVIY TA’LIM TIZIMINI
RIVOJLANTIRISH VA UNGA QARATILGAN
KREATIV G’OYALAR,
TAKLIFLAR VA YECHIMLAR”**

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE QUALITIES OF ENDURANCE AND SPEED IN PRE- CONSCRIPTION YOUTH

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Abstract: *This article is intended for students (cadets) of the Faculty of Military Training and Physical Education of higher educational institutions, as well as for teachers on the subject of pre-conscription military training. The purpose of the article: to provide information on the development of the qualities of endurance and speed in pre-conscription youth.*

Keywords: *adaptation, preparation, program, staff, system, complex.*

Endurance development

Endurance is usually understood as the ability to effectively perform an exercise, overcoming fatigue.

Endurance is caused by many factors, primarily by the activity of the cerebral cortex, which regulates the state of the central nervous system and the performance of all other organs and systems of the body engaged. An important role in the system of pre-conscription training is played by the development of strong-willed qualities of young people, since they, being the result of conscious activity, are associated with the functions of the central nervous system and largely determine the effectiveness of classes and the success of performances in competitions in military-applied sports that require endurance.

There are general and special endurance: the first is part of the general physical training, the second is part of the special physical training of pre-conscription youth.

General endurance – is the ability to perform effective and prolonged work of a non-specific nature, in which a significant part of the muscular apparatus is involved. Such work places increased demands on the cardiovascular, respiratory and central nervous systems. General endurance allows you to successfully cope with any long-term work of high or moderate power and serves as the basis for the development of special endurance.

Special endurance - is the ability to effectively perform work and overcome fatigue in conditions determined by the requirements of competitive activity in a particular applied sport.

Special endurance is not only the ability to counteract fatigue, but also the ability to perform a task in conditions of strictly limited distance (running, skiing, swimming and other cyclical sports) or for a certain time (wrestling, etc.).

The optimal way to develop endurance is to first lay a solid foundation, and then develop special endurance on its basis. In parallel, they solve the tasks of psychological training, technical improvement, education of strength, speed, dexterity, despite the fact that these components are not related to the physiological mechanisms of endurance.

General endurance provides aerobic capabilities that cause long-term performance of work, including in a mixed mode. These opportunities are also needed for the rapid recovery

of the student's body, especially after an anaerobic load. Rapid recovery allows you to reduce the rest interval between repetitions, increase their number and perform exercises with high intensity.

In the program of general physical training of a pre-conscript, general endurance is acquired through moderate-intensity physical exercises, including special ones (running, cross-country running, skiing, swimming). During such work, the organs and systems of the student's body, especially the cardiovascular and respiratory, are significantly strengthened, their functions are improved.

The education of general endurance is achieved by performing long-term work of moderate intensity of an aerobic nature. At the same time, the heart rate for the poorly prepared should not exceed 130 beats / min, and for the more prepared — 150-160 beats / min. In this case, not only long-term performance of work is ensured, but also its performance without excessive neuropsychic stresses at a high emotional level. At the same time, not only increases the efficiency of the cardiovascular system and other body systems, but also what is very important, the musculoskeletal system is prepared, muscles and ligaments are strengthened, their elasticity and attachment strength are improved, pain prevention in the liver, spleen, Achilles tendon is provided.

The development of speed

The concept of "speed" characterizes the ability to move at the maximum possible speed and includes: the actual speed of movements, their frequency, the ability to accelerate and the speed of motor reaction.

The main prerequisites for speed are the mobility of nervous processes, high-speed strength, extensibility and elasticity of muscles, the degree of mastery of movement techniques, the intensity of volitional effort and biomechanical processes that ensure high-speed movements.

Speed can be general and special. The development of general speed is presented in the general physical training program. *Special quickness* – is the ability to perform movement (applied exercise) with the required, usually high speed.

In applied physical training, the *speed of motor reaction* is important – the ability to react as quickly as possible to the sound, movement of the enemy, weapons, changing external conditions, etc. It is known that under the influence of training on the speed of motor reaction, the time between the signal and the response action decreases. Having reached the limit, it stabilizes, but depending on the state of the central nervous system and the motor apparatus, it may change slightly.

General development and special exercises are used to educate pre-conscripts in speed.

Special exercises for the education of speed consist of fast movements, as close as possible to applied exercises and their elements.

These exercises can be divided into three groups: cyclic, acyclic and mixed.

- *Cyclic exercises* are performed repeatedly with the greatest possible frequency of movements (running, running on the spot in a stop, jumping, skiing, etc.).

- *Acyclic exercises* are performed repeatedly with maximum speed (blows, jerks, jumps, swings, etc.).

- *Mixed exercises* are performed repeatedly (jumping and throwing with a running start, individual actions in sports games, etc.).

Applied exercises performed with maximum intensity in normal, light and difficult conditions are important for the education of speed among pre-conscript youth. After performing these exercises in complicated conditions, they proceed to their performance in normal conditions.

In order to increase the maximum speed of movement and the frequency of movements, a sound and accelerating rhythm are used. The best effect is achieved when moving in light conditions under musical accompaniment with an accelerating rhythm.

When performing speed exercises, the role of mental mood, will and direction of the thoughts of the pre-conscript, as well as emotional uplift, which is achieved using the competitive method, is extremely important.

For the education of speed, the repeated method is most often used.

In addition to the general provisions of training and training, the following should be taken into account:

- the decisive factor for the education of speed is the high intensity of movements. The student should strive with the help of the maximum possible mobilization of forces and the optimal frequency and amplitude of movements corresponding to his physique to reach his highest speed or exceed it. This should happen in full accordance with the level of mastering the technique. To do this, it is necessary to form a technique with increasing intensity of movements;

- the duration of the exercise and the number of repetitions should be such that there is no decrease in speed. On average, loads of maximum intensity in one lesson are repeated from 5 to 10 times;

- the duration of rest pauses between exercises should ensure that the pre-conscript is ready to repeat the same work without reducing speed. On the other hand, the interval should not be so long that the excitement in the nervous system drops excessively. Depending on the intensity and duration of exposure and individual ability to recover, the duration of the interval between a series of exercises can be set from 4 to 6 minutes;

- the performance of work aimed at fostering speed should end as soon as the objective indicators of the stopwatch indicate a decrease in speed. However, this work can continue to a greater extent to develop endurance and strengthen skeletal muscles and to a lesser extent to improve technique.

- the duration of exposure should reach an optimal value. for example, in running, the highest speed is reached between the 5th and 6th seconds. The length of the distance at which they run at the maximum speed or at 1% lower speed is, depending on the level of achievements of the student, from 20 to 45 m.

Considering that high-speed stimuli are most effective with optimal excitability of the nervous system, it is necessary to build classes so that high-speed exercises in a separate

lesson are not preceded by tedious work. Therefore, after the introductory part, you need to immediately move on to the most effective high-speed loads.

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